

- 1 This document presents the corrections made on the first version of the draft following the
- 2 proofreading of the OFB and FEE.
- 3 The changes resulting from the OFB review are in green, those resulting from the FEE review
- 4 are in blue, and those resulting from the review of both are in red.

5 **Drivers of bat activity at wind turbines advocate for mitigating bat**
6 **fatality risk using multicriteria algorithm-based curtailment**

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25 Running title: Mitigating bat-wind turbine fatality risk

26 **Abstract**

27 Wind turbine development is growing exponentially and faster than other sources of renewable
28 energy worldwide. While wind farms have small footprint they are not free from negative
29 impacts on wildlife. This is particularly true for long-lived insectivorous bats, whose population
30 viability ~~are~~ can be threatened by wind turbines through mortality events due to collision and
31 barotrauma. Conventional wind turbine curtailment at low wind speeds (i.e. when bats are
32 active and when energy production is low) can reduce fatality risks, but show variable and
33 incomplete effectiveness because other factors could also affect bat fatality risks including
34 landscape features, temperature, wind turbine functioning, and seasonality. The joint effects of
35 these drivers, and their combined use as criteria in algorithm-based curtailment, have so far
36 received little attention in the context of wind turbine impact mitigation. Here, we compiled
37 and analysed bat acoustic data recorded at wind turbine nacelles in a context of post-
38 construction regulatory studies at 59 sites in metropolitan France and for roughly 15,000 full
39 nights over four years. We modelled nightly bat activity – which links to fatality risk – in
40 relation to its multiple drivers for three bat guilds, and assessed whether curtailment of wind
41 turbines based on these models would be more efficient to limit the fatality risk than
42 conventional curtailment such as those based on unique wind speed thresholds. Our findings
43 revealed that landscape features, weather conditions and seasonality, together with wind turbine
44 functioning determine bat activity at nacelles. Algorithm-based curtailment proves to be more
45 efficient than conventional wind speed curtailment, and has the potential of drastically reducing
46 fatality risk while sustaining the same energy production. As an example, for a 20% loss of
47 blade rotations, the algorithm curtailment exhibits 13 to 45% less bat activity at risk, depending
48 on bat guilds, compared to wind speed curtailment. These findings call for the use of curtailment
49 based on algorithms instead of conventional wind speed criteria as both the power production
50 and the benefit for biodiversity will be higher in most situations.

- 51 **Key words:** acoustic monitoring; chiroptera; cut-in speed; collision risk; mitigation hierarchy;
- 52 wind energy

53 1. Introduction

54 Wind power generation produces near-zero greenhouse gas emissions during the operational
55 phase, has weak greenhouse gas payback time, and constitutes an efficient and sustainable way
56 for energy transition (Dammeier et al., 2019; Veers et al., 2019). As a consequence and in line
57 with international treaties such as the 2016 Paris agreement to reduce global greenhouse gas
58 emissions, wind turbine installation has grown exponentially over the last 20 years and currently
59 represents the most rapidly expanding form of renewable energy worldwide (GWEC, 2021).
60 While wind farm installation ~~has~~ can have a relatively small footprint in terms of land
61 conversion compared to other development projects, it is not free from negative impacts on
62 wildlife, particularly for long-lived insectivorous bats through mortality events by collision and
63 barotrauma. Such increases in mortality are likely to impinge on the viability of populations
64 (Frick et al., 2017; Friedenbergr and Frick, 2021). This is especially true for migratory and long-
65 range echolocating bat species, which are the most sensitive to collisions and barotrauma as
66 they fly more often at height (Roemer et al., 2017). In addition to mortality, wind farms reduce
67 habitat availability by decreasing the attractiveness of their adjacent areas (Barré et al., 2018).

68 In the European Union and in many countries worldwide, wind energy developers must carry
69 out an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) prior to any wind farm installation to assess
70 potential environmental consequences and the measures required to avoid impacts. Developers
71 must also monitor impacts during the operational phase (Directive 2011/92/EU). However, pre-
72 construction EIAs currently can fail to predict bat fatalities with accuracy (Lintott et al., 2016),
73 and guidelines to avoid “areas where high bat activity has been determined by impact
74 assessment” (EUROBATS; Rodrigues et al., 2015) appear to be poorly implemented, at least
75 in some areas with high densities of attractive habitats for bats (Barré et al., 2018). When
76 impacts cannot be spatially avoided, reduction and as a last resort offsetting measures must be
77 implemented to achieve no net loss of biodiversity (i.e. the mitigation hierarchy framework

78 proposed by the Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme). Wind turbine curtailment at
79 low wind speeds – when bats are highly active and energy production is low – constitutes a
80 reduction measure that offer promising opportunities to reconcile bat conservation and wind
81 energy (Voigt et al., 2015). ~~The most widespread~~One of the most basic curtailment strategies
82 is based on a simple wind speed criterion (mainly wind speed thresholds between 3.5 and 8
83 m/s), below which the turbine is stopped due to expected favourable conditions for bats. This
84 approach can significantly reduce the fatality risk, but shows variable and incomplete
85 effectiveness (Adams et al., 2021; Whitby et al., 2021). Besides wind speeds, landscape features
86 and other weather factors such as temperature and rain also drive bat fatality risk (Santos et al.,
87 2013; Thompson et al., 2017). In addition, bat activity at wind turbine nacelles, which links to
88 fatality risk (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2013; Peterson et al., 2021), also depends on the weather,
89 season, landscape features, and wind turbine dimensions and rotation speed (Behr et al., 2017;
90 Brinkmann et al., 2011; Cryan et al., 2014; Horn et al., 2008; Roemer et al., 2019).
91 Consequently, curtailment strategies based on multifactor algorithms are potentially more
92 efficient in reducing the fatality risk. Indeed, the use of an algorithm to curtail wind turbines in
93 real time based on weather factors, date and nightly time, should allow to avoid most collisions
94 while minimizing the loss of production (Behr et al., 2017).

95 Behr et al. (2017) and Brinkmann et al. (2011) are ones of the rare available studies that
96 proposed a multicriteria framework to curtail wind turbine. These studies were based on data
97 sampled in 2008 in Germany covering 6 months at 70 wind turbines and 35 different sites. To
98 our knowledge, no peer-reviewed study has examined simultaneously and on a
99 spatiotemporally extensive dataset of bat activity at nacelle height the joint effects of all factors
100 influencing bat fatality risk (i.e. landscape features, weather conditions, date, and wind turbine
101 characteristics), neither assessed the possibility to use such factors simultaneously in algorithms
102 specific to different bat guilds to curtail wind turbines.

103 To assess the possibility of using multicriteria curtailment algorithms, we compiled bat acoustic
104 data recorded at wind turbine nacelles by wind energy developers in a context of post-
105 construction regulatory studies, while homogeneously re-analysing acoustic data at 59 sites in
106 France and for roughly 15,000 entire nights. Reprocessed bat acoustic data allowed to build a
107 standardized bat activity metric at nacelle height known to be a good predictor of fatality risk
108 (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2013; Peterson et al., 2021). Given the absence of national guidelines
109 concerning the characteristics and settings of bat recorders for bat monitoring at nacelles and
110 the large amount of engineering consultants involved in data collection, we expected a large
111 variation in the methods (Coly et al., 2017). Thus, our first objective was to assess whether
112 monitoring methods (devices and settings) or confounding effects with landscape features, date,
113 weather and wind turbine characteristics would bias comparison of bat activity between sites.
114 This assessment was intended to filter out some sites if necessary. Once any method bias was
115 controlled for, our second objective was to determine the main factors influencing bat activity
116 at nacelles. We expected bat activity to increase with increasing landscape quality (e.g. by an
117 increasing amount of forests, proximity to wetlands or land use heterogeneity; Boughey et al.,
118 2011a; Put et al., 2019; Sirami et al., 2013) and decreasing blade rotation speed (Cryan et al.,
119 2014; Horn et al., 2008), and to be higher during nights with good weather conditions (i.e. high
120 temperature, low wind speed and no rain; Erickson and West, 2002; Voigt et al., 2015) and at
121 the end of summer (Heim et al., 2016). Finally, our third objective was to compare on a nightly
122 scale the performance of a curtailment algorithm based on multiple factors to that of a
123 conventional single-criterion curtailment method based on wind speed thresholds, in terms of
124 both bat fatality risk and energy production. We expected the algorithm-based curtailment to
125 be more efficient in reducing fatality risks compared to conventional curtailment, by avoiding
126 a larger percentage of bat activity occurring when blades are moving, while involving lower
127 losses of energy production.

128 2. Methods

129 2.1. Acoustic data collection and processing

130 We compiled existing raw acoustic data (i.e. sound files [in raw or wav format](#)) of 14,937
131 complete recording nights at 59 wind turbine nacelles located on 55 wind farms in France (Fig.
132 1; Table S1). These data were provided by nine wind farm developers and produced by 12
133 consulting firms and non-governmental organizations as part of regulatory post-implementation
134 impact monitoring studies. Each of the 59 sites was monitored on average for 251 nights (min:
135 103; max: 514). The monitored nights covered all months of the year and span four years
136 between 2017 and 2020. The year 2017 represents 2% of nights, the 2018 18% of nights, the
137 2019 79% of nights and the 2020 0.4% of nights (Fig. S1).

138 Three types of recorders were used: Batcorder at 18 sites (versions 1, 2 and 3; ecoObs),
139 Batmode S+ at 34 sites (bat bioacoustics technology GmbH) and Song Meters at eight sites
140 (SM3BAT and SM4BAT; Wildlife Acoustics). Each was associated with one to three triggering
141 thresholds, i.e. a built-in recording control algorithm of the recorder which started the recording
142 when a sound event exceeded a given sound level (see Supporting information S1 for more
143 details).

144 Acoustic monitoring was always performed over the entire nights, from sunset to sunrise. We
145 used the number of bat passes (hereafter referred to as “activity”) or the presence/absence
146 (hereafter referred to as “occurrence”) recorded during a night as a measure of bat visits with
147 fatality risk (see section 2.3 for more details). We defined a bat pass as one or more echolocation
148 calls within a five-second interval. Each [949,418,731,717](#) bat passes were automatically
149 classified to the closest taxonomic level using the Tadarida software (Bas et al., 2017). Since
150 most bat species had very low occurrence (Table S1), we pooled together species into three
151 guilds based on their similar echolocation call structures and therefore similar foraging
152 strategies: long-range echolocators (LRE), mid-range echolocators (MRE) and short-range

153 echolocators (SRE) (Frey-Ehrenbold et al., 2013), see Table S2 for species composition. Long-
154 range echolocators are especially sensitive to fatality risks with wind turbines due to the great
155 part of the time they spend at height [\(i.e. 20 to 45 m above the ground\)](#), followed by the mid-
156 range echolocators (Table S2; Roemer et al., 2017). Although the grouping of species into these
157 three guilds prevented misidentification problems between cryptic species, many interferences
158 in the nacelle due to wind turbine functioning generated many false positives, especially at very
159 high blade speeds. We followed the approach of Barré et al. (2019) and applied a maximum
160 false positive tolerance of 50% to discard these interferences (see Barré et al. (2019) for more
161 details), [which reduced the dataset to 98,627 bat passes](#).

162

163 *2.2. Environmental and wind turbine variables*

164 To determine which factors influence bat activity and occurrence at wind turbine nacelles, we
165 collected or computed variables related to landscape composition and heterogeneity, weather
166 conditions, and wind turbine functioning and dimensions.

167 *Landscape variables* - We considered the following five land-uses that are known to positively
168 or negatively affect bats: impervious surfaces (Azam et al., 2016; Dixon, 2011), arable lands
169 (Put et al., 2019), grasslands (Froidevaux et al., 2017; Lentini et al., 2012; Roeleke et al., 2016),
170 forests (Boughey et al., 2011a; Heim et al., 2017) and water bodies (De Conno et al., 2018;
171 Sirami et al., 2013). These variables were computed around the 59 monitoring sites as
172 proportions of total area for variables with enough variations (impervious surfaces, arable lands,
173 grasslands and forests), in ten area buffers around sites (50, 100, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 3000,
174 4000, 5000 and 10000 m radius) to use the most relevant scale for each variable (Kalda et al.,
175 2015, see Statistical Analysis section for more details). We also calculated the Euclidean
176 distance to the nearest impervious surfaces, forests and water bodies. Moreover, we computed
177 landscape metrics depicting landscape configurational and compositional heterogeneity

178 (Monck-Whipp et al., 2017), including edge density (i.e. the density of ecotones in m/ha),
179 conditional entropy (i.e. an increasing index with increasing landscape complexity), patch
180 richness density (i.e. the number of patch types standardized by the surface), and Shannon
181 diversity index of habitat patches. These landscape metrics were computed using the R package
182 *landscapemetrics* (Hesselbarth et al., 2019), and for the ten radius sizes presented above. All
183 landscape variables were extracted from the high-resolution CES OSO land cover map 2018
184 available at <https://www.theia-land.fr/en/ceslist/land-cover-sec/> (Derksen et al., 2020).

185 *Weather variables* - We collected the average wind speed (m/s) and temperature (°C) recorded
186 by wind turbine nacelle weather stations in 10-minute intervals and averaged them on a nightly
187 scale at each site (i.e. on the same scale as acoustic data). Since the amount of rainfall was not
188 recorded by the nacelle weather stations, we collected the daily cumulated rain (mm) (i.e. over
189 the 24 hour period from midnight of the day when the recording night started) using the weather
190 database from E-OBS
191 (https://surfobs.climate.copernicus.eu/dataaccess/access_eobs.php#datafiles).

192 *Wind turbines variables* - We collected dimensions of wind turbines which measured 45 to 139
193 m (92 m in average) in nacelle height and 44 to 126 m (94 m in average) in rotor diameter
194 (Table S1) (Cryan and Barclay, 2009). We also collected the average rotation speed (km/h) at
195 the tip of the blade in 10-minute intervals, and averaged it on a nightly scale at each site.

196

197 2.3. Statistical analysis

198 We assessed drivers of measures of bat activity and occurrence around wind turbine nacelles,
199 including factors related to landscape composition and heterogeneity, weather conditions, the
200 Julian day, wind turbine functioning and dimensions and also recording methods (i.e. the
201 recorder type and the trigger sensitivity). In a first step, since we compiled data produced by

202 different contributors, we expected the existence of multiple combinations between the recorder
203 type and the trigger sensitivity. However, these recording methods deeply affect the amount of
204 bat passes recorded (Adams et al., 2012). Confounding effects between recording methods and
205 factors of interest (e.g. landscape composition) could prevent to model them simultaneously.
206 We therefore tested for trends in landscape composition and heterogeneity, weather conditions,
207 and wind turbine functioning and dimensions between recording methods (i.e. a discrete
208 variable including seven combinations between the recorder type and the trigger sensitivity),
209 using Kruskal-Wallis tests and box plots. We then computed the proportion of variance
210 explained by each variable (*pseudo-R*²) to assess whether the importance of the factors of
211 interest (actual drivers of bat activity) was biased by the different recording methods. To
212 properly study the drivers of bat activity at wind turbine nacelles, a prerequisite is that the
213 recording methods do not capture an overwhelming part of the variance compared to the factors
214 known to affect bat activity. To achieve this, we built one full Generalized Linear Mixed Model
215 (GLMM, R package *glmmTMB*; Brooks et al., 2017) per bat guild, using LRE and MRE activity
216 and SRE occurrence as response variables, and the landscape (see Supporting information S2
217 for landscape variable selection and composition), weather conditions (i.e. average wind speed,
218 average temperature and cumulated rain), the Julian day, and wind turbine functioning (i.e.
219 average blades rotation speed) and dimensions (i.e. nacelle height and rotor diameter) as fixed
220 effects (hereafter referred to as “explanatory variables”). Since we had a relatively small
221 number of sites (i.e. 59), we restricted the number of landscape variables to three; i.e. the same
222 number than the other types of variables (i.e. three weather variables and three wind turbine
223 functioning and dimension variables available). For landscape variables we pre-selected the
224 best computing area buffer and in a second step selected the three ones – within the five
225 landscape variables –with the best conjoint contributions (see Supporting Information S2 for
226 more details). We used the site identifier as random effect to account for pseudo-replication

227 (i.e. many recording nights per site), associated with a negative binomial distribution for LRE
228 and MRE guilds and a binomial distribution for SRE guild (see Supporting information S2 and
229 Table S4 for composition of full models). Then, we computed the *pseudo-R*² of each variable
230 by subtracting the *marginal R*² of the full model and that of the model without the target
231 variable, using the R package *sjstats*.

232 The preliminary analysis showed that recording methods resulted in confounding effects with
233 most other variables of interest and captured the largest variance part (Table S5; Figs. 2 & S2).
234 Thus, in order to model bat activity or occurrence as a function of explanatory variables, we
235 selected in a second step only one combination between the recorder type and the trigger
236 sensitivity that removed any variation in recording methods. We chose the combination
237 constituted of the Batmode set to a trigger sensitivity of 37 dB SPL which had the largest dataset
238 resulting in 34 sites, 8,619 nights and 65,775 bat passes. Based on this subset, we performed
239 the same GLMMs workflow than presented above (see Supporting information S2 and Table
240 S6 for more details) to assess respective effects of explanatory variables on the LRE and MRE
241 activity and SRE occurrence. For each explanatory variable, we checked the potential need for
242 adding a non-linear effect by visual inspection of Generalized Additive Mixed Models
243 (GAMM, R package *mgcv*; Wood, 2011; see Table 1 for variables which required quadratic or
244 cubic effects). We also checked the absence of multicollinearity by calculating the Variance
245 Inflation Factor (VIF) for each explanatory variable (R package *performance*; Lüdtke et al.,
246 2021). All variables showed a VIF < 2, safely implying there was no evidence of
247 multicollinearity (Chatterjee and Hadi, 2006). Overall model validation was then performed
248 using diagnostic plots (R packages *DHARMA* and *performance*; Lüdtke et al., 2021). Full
249 models were compared to null ones using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) (Burnham
250 and Anderson, 2002), and goodness-of-fit was assessed using the marginal *R*² (variance
251 explained by the fixed effects) and conditional *R*² (variance explained by both fixed and random

252 factors) values (Nakagawa and Schielzeth, 2013). All analyses were performed using a
253 significance threshold of 5% in R statistical software v.4.0.3 (R Core Team, 2020).

254

255 *2.4. Assessing the effectiveness of using model equations to limit the fatality risk compared to*
256 *conventional curtailments*

257 [Using the same Batmode dataset](#), ~~W~~We assessed whether curtailment of wind turbines based on
258 multiple-factor models could be more efficient to limit the fatality risk at the scale of all sites
259 than commonly used curtailment methods based on wind speed only. For that, we trained full
260 models for each guild on a 50% fully random subset of the dataset (hereafter referred to as
261 “training dataset”) and predicted bat activity on the other 50% (hereafter referred to as
262 “prediction dataset”), and this 100 times. Then, we computed for each prediction dataset the
263 remaining percentage of bat activity (for LRE and MRE guilds) or occurrence (for SRE guild)
264 at risk (i.e. the real bat activity or occurrence recorded while the blades were moving) and the
265 percentage of lost blade rotations (i.e. as a proxy of lost energy production) resulting of stopping
266 wind turbines following either of two methods: (i) curtailing above thresholds of bat activity
267 predicted from full models (hereafter referred to as “multicriteria curtailment algorithm”), and
268 (ii) curtailing below wind speed thresholds (hereafter referred to as “wind speed curtailment”).
269 Finally, we plotted the relationship between the remaining percentage of bat activity or
270 occurrence at risk and the percentage of lost blade rotations for both curtailment methods to
271 evaluate their respective effectiveness in limiting fatality risks (Fig. 3A).

272 To assess whether the effectiveness was relevant for all sites, we also plotted the relationship
273 between the remaining percentage of bat activity at risk and the percentage of lost blade
274 rotations for each site independently, and computed Area Under Curve (AUC) values for both
275 curtailment methods in order to evaluate the most effective one (i.e. the higher AUC value) (R
276 package *MESS*). We also estimated to what extent the effectiveness of curtailment methods was

277 preserved when sites included in the training dataset were different from sites included in the
278 prediction dataset. For that, we repeated the procedure explained above, but using a training
279 dataset constituted of data from 33 out of 34 sites and a prediction dataset constituted of data
280 from the 34th site, and we repeated it for each site in order to present its results while computing
281 AUC values for both curtailment methods. These site-by-site assessments were only made for
282 LRE and MRE guilds for which we had enough data for each site.

283 Finally, because the percentage of lost blade rotations is not a perfect proxy of lost energy
284 production, we assessed whether the relative comparison of lost blade rotations between
285 curtailment methods as a proxy of energy production losses was biased (e.g. one method for a
286 given level of lost blade rotations involving slower blade speeds, and in turn lower energy
287 losses, than the other method). For that we compared the distribution of blade speeds inside lost
288 blade rotations between both curtailment methods.

289 3. Results

290 3.1. Bat monitoring

291 A total 98,627 bat passes were recorded in the 59 study sites and 14,937 nights. However, as
292 described above, in order to avoid confounding effects between recording methods and other
293 explanatory variables, we only selected sites monitored using Batmode recorders which
294 exhibited no trigger sensitivity variation, while including most of the data (i.e. 34 sites out of
295 59 and 8,619 nights out of 14,937). Data from Batmode resulted in a total 65,775 bat passes
296 recorded, with 43,519 passes of LRE, 22,135 passes of MRE and 121 passes of SRE. The LRE
297 guild was composed of 79%, 20% and 1% of *Nyctalus leislerii*, *Nyctalus noctula*, and
298 *Eptesicus serotinus*, respectively, while MRE guild was composed of 62%, 26% and 9% of
299 *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, *Pipistrellus nathusii* and *Pipistrellus kuhlii*, respectively. SRE guild
300 was composed of 63%, 25% and 12% of *Myotis* spp., *Plecotus* spp. and *Barbastella*
301 *barbastellus*, respectively. At least one pass of LRE, MRE and SRE was recorded in 35%, 18%
302 and 1% of nights, respectively (Table S3).

303

304 3.2. Drivers of bat activity around nacelles

305 Full models of bat activity and occurrence showed smaller AIC than null models (delta AIC of
306 full models from -49 to -1536), with 44%, 54% and 54% variance explained by fixed effects
307 and 71%, 60% and 56% by both fixed and random effects, for LRE, MRE and SRE guilds,
308 respectively (Table S6).

309 Regarding landscape variables, LRE activity was positively affected by the landscape Shannon
310 diversity index of habitat patches at 10,000 m radius scale while MRE activity increased with
311 increasing patch richness density at 1,000 m radius scale and forest proportion at 10,000 m
312 radius scale. We also found significant positive relationships between SRE occurrence and edge

313 density at 10,000 m radius scale and the proportion of impervious surfaces at 100 m radius scale
314 (Fig. 4; Table 1). Concerning wind turbine functioning and dimensions, increasing average
315 blade speed significantly reduced the activity/occurrence of all guilds, and rotor diameter
316 positively affected the occurrence of SRE guild, while no effect of nacelle height was found
317 (Figs. 4 & S3; Table 1). Concerning weather conditions, average temperature positively
318 affected the activity of LRE and MRE guilds, while the average wind speed and the cumulated
319 rain had negative effects on the activity/occurrence of all guilds (Fig. 4; Table 1). Finally, we
320 found seasonality in the activity of the LRE and MRE guilds, manifested as a cubic and
321 quadratic relationship, respectively, with the Julian date: increasing between January and
322 August, and decreasing from September to December (Fig. 4; Table 1).

323

324 *3.3. Effectiveness of model equations to limit the fatality risk compared to conventional* 325 *curtailments*

326 For the wind speed curtailment, we found that increasing wind speed thresholds below which
327 wind turbines should be stopped almost always linearly decreases the real bat activity at risk
328 for all guilds (Fig. S4A-C). For the multicriteria curtailment algorithm, we found that
329 decreasing the predicted bat activity above which wind turbines should be stopped decreased
330 the actual bat activity or occurrence at risk: exponentially for LRE activity, logistically for MRE
331 activity and linearly for SRE occurrence. (Fig. S4A-C). Moreover, expanding curtailment
332 increased the percentage of lost blade rotations differently between methods: with logistic
333 increases when using a wind speed criterion, and exponential increases when using multicriteria
334 curtailment algorithm. (Fig. 4D-F).

335 When we linked the real bat activity or occurrence at risk with the percentage of lost blade
336 rotations, we found that the multicriteria curtailment algorithm was more efficient than wind
337 speed curtailment for all guilds (Fig. 3B). As an example, for a 20% loss of blade rotations, we

338 found that the multicriteria curtailment algorithm at the scale of all sites exhibited on average
339 $37\pm 4\%$ and $13\pm 5\%$ less bat activity and $45\pm 11\%$ less occurrence at risk than wind speed
340 curtailment for LRE, MRE and SRE guilds, respectively (Fig. 3B). The higher efficiency of
341 multicriteria curtailment algorithm was confirmed by its AUC values which were higher than
342 those of wind speed curtailment at 78 % and 69% of sites for LRE and MRE guilds, respectively
343 (Figs. S5 & S6). Finally, when the algorithm was trained on 33 out of 34 sites and predictions
344 made on the remaining site (i.e. model training and predictions based on independent sites),
345 algorithm curtailment had higher AUC values than wind speed curtailment at 88 and 84% of
346 sites for LRE and MRE, respectively (Fig. S7 & S8).

347 Finally, blade speed distributions do not differ between lost blade rotations of both curtailment
348 methods, meaning that the relative comparison of lost blade rotations between curtailment
349 methods as a proxy of energy production losses is not biased (Fig. S9).

350

351 4. Discussion

352 The identification of drivers of bat fatality risk with wind turbines from acoustic monitoring at
353 nacelles, and the possibility of their combined use as criteria in algorithm-based curtailment,
354 have so far received little attention [in the scientific literature](#) in the context of wind turbine
355 impact mitigation. Our study shows that, when using acoustic data continuously produced in
356 post-construction regulatory studies, recording methods should be accounted for before
357 analysing the drivers of bat fatality risk. Once detection method biases were avoided, results
358 showed that it is possible to disentangle the main drivers. Our findings revealed that landscape
359 features, weather conditions and seasonality, together with wind turbine functioning determine
360 [the bat activity of all bat guilds](#) at nacelles. Algorithms including all these drivers to stop wind
361 turbines above a given level of predicted bat activity are more efficient than common
362 curtailment methods based on wind speed thresholds, as they reduce more fatality risk while
363 sustaining the same energy production.

364

365 4.1. Assessing bias in recording methods

366 One of the aims of this study was to take advantage of the numerous pre-existing data from
367 post-construction monitoring studies instead of designing a field study that would require
368 paramount monetary and time investments. A prerequisite for using all aggregated data was the
369 absence biases related to the recording methods. Unfortunately, when considering data
370 collected using different recording methods, the combination of recorder type and triggering
371 sensitivity explained much more variance than all well-known drivers of bat activity (Behr et
372 al., 2017; Cryan et al., 2014; Horn et al., 2008; Roemer et al., 2019), minimizing their relative
373 importance in the models. All gradients of drivers strongly varied among recorder type/trigger
374 sensitivity combinations, thus preventing any modelling of the effects of drivers on bat activity
375 based on the full dataset due to confounding effects. Indeed, different recorder type/trigger

376 sensitivity combinations can lead to very different levels of bat activity between sites due to the
377 different detection distances generated by the material specificities and settings (Adams et al.,
378 2012; Darras et al., 2020). We opted to compensate for this problem by modelling the effect of
379 the drivers on bat activity after separating the recorder type/trigger sensitivity combinations.
380 However, a harmonization of monitoring methods across all sites would avoid such partitioning
381 and loss of data. Alternatively, future studies could assess the possibility of using corrective
382 coefficients of activity between different recorder type/trigger sensitivity combinations, or
383 establish longer bat pass units, in order to make the sites monitored in different ways
384 comparable.

385

386 *4.2. Drivers of bat activity around nacelles*

387 Our results highlight the high importance of accounting for all drivers (i.e. landscape, wind
388 turbine functioning, weather, and date) to better account for the variation of bat activity at
389 nacelle height. As expected from previous studies looking at fatality risk or bat activity at
390 nacelle height, we found a joint effect of all types of drivers on bat activity (Behr et al., 2017;
391 Cryan et al., 2014; Horn et al., 2008; Santos et al., 2013; Thompson et al., 2017).

392 Specifically, LRE and MRE activity increased with Shannon diversity index of habitat patches
393 and patch richness density, respectively, as previously reported by (Froidevaux et al., 2022;
394 Mendes et al., 2017; Monck-Whipp et al., 2017). Edge density also positively affected the SRE
395 guild occurrence, as previously documented with respect to hedgerow density (Lacoeuilhe et
396 al., 2016; Verboom and Huitema, 1997) or to density of all edge habitat (Ancillotto et al., 2017;
397 Mendes et al., 2017). We also found forest cover to positively affect MRE activity, consistently
398 with Roemer et al. (2019), who showed that bat activity at height decreased with the distance
399 to forest, and with Boughey et al. (2011a) who found higher bat activity at ground level with
400 an increasing proportion of forest. Unexpectedly, our model revealed a positive effect of

401 impervious habitat proportion on SRE activity, a relationship which is elsewhere described as
402 negative (Gili et al., 2020). Impervious habitat in this dataset corresponds to roads and the buffer
403 scale selected is very local (100m). It is likely that this is an indirect positive effect related to
404 ecotone/hedge~~re~~ow associated to roads (i.e. road access to wind turbine), a favourable context
405 for foraging of narrow- and edge-space foragers of the SRE guild (Denzinger and Schnitzler,
406 2013).

407 Increasing blade rotation speed logistically reduced LRE activity and SRE occurrence, and
408 linearly decreased MRE activity, in accordance with previous studies (Cryan et al., 2014; Horn
409 et al., 2008). It should be noted that it is unlikely that this result fully mirrors the effect of wind
410 speed (Fig. S109). Indeed, the negative effect of blade rotation speed is preserved at both high
411 and low wind speeds (Fig. S110). We also found a positive effect of rotor diameter on SRE
412 occurrence for which we have no explanation. However, this result should be interpreted with
413 caution as the variation of the predicted probability of presence is extremely low, i.e. ranged
414 below a probability of presence of 0.003 (Fig. S3), as well as the total number of SRE passes
415 (i.e. 121 passes).

416 Regarding weather conditions, increasing temperatures promoted the activity of LRE and MRE
417 guilds, while increasing wind speeds and cumulated rain suppressed the activity of all guilds.
418 These results corroborate studies of bat activity at height, showing very similar patterns (Arnett
419 et al., 2006; Behr et al., 2017; Horn et al., 2008; Redell et al., 2006). Interestingly, both LRE
420 and MRE guilds exhibited some tolerance to unfavourable weather conditions, with a non-
421 negligible proportion of remaining activity in such conditions (see Fig. S124). For instance,
422 above wind speeds of 8m/s, 9% of MRE activity and 12% of LRE activity remained; below a
423 temperature of 10°C, 2% of MRE activity and 7% of LRE activity remained (Fig. S124), which
424 is highly consistent with findings by Behr et al. (2017) in Germany.

425 With respect to seasonality, a peak in LRE and MRE activity was detected in August, thus
426 reinforcing previous studies reporting a peak in bat fatalities at wind turbines in this period
427 (Arnett et al., 2008; Schuster et al., 2015).

428

429 *4.3. Assessing the effectiveness of using model equations to limit the fatality risk compared to* 430 *conventional curtailments*

431 The multifactor responses of bat activity and occurrence at wind turbine nacelles reported in
432 this study highlight the crucial need of curtailment strategies based on all possible combinations
433 of the driving factors, while proving that curtailment based on a unique fixed environmental
434 threshold such as cut-in wind speeds is not fully effective to avoid fatality risks.

435 Based on the relationship between the percentage of recorded bat activity or occurrence and the
436 percentage of lost blade rotations entailed by each curtailment threshold (i.e. a wind speed value
437 for conventional curtailment and a predicted bat activity and occurrence value for multicriteria
438 curtailment algorithm), for a given level of ~~lost~~ loss of energy production blade rotations,
439 multicriteria curtailment algorithm will save many more bats from fatality risk (i.e. in average
440 between 13, 37 and 45% less fatality risk for MRE, LRE and SRE guilds, respectively, for a
441 20% loss of blade rotations). This result corroborates conclusions from Behr et al. (2017) who
442 performed a similar assessment using the real loss of energy production and curtailment
443 thresholds based on a mean number of fatalities per turbine and per year.

444

445 *4.4. Limitations and recommendations*

446 The study calls for prudence when using data from different recording methods that should be
447 controlled before any modelling as they could strongly bias the algorithm to use for curtailment.

448 This requires regulatory databases (as it is the case with the DEPOBIO tool in France;

449 <https://depot-legal-biodiversite.naturefrance.fr/>) to demand the input of metadata related to the
450 methods used, or ideally to harmonize these methods.

451 To go further in the modelling of bat fatality risks, the curtailment algorithm method should be
452 deployed on a fine, intra-night scale, in order to get as close as possible to real-time curtailment
453 and minimize production losses (Behr et al., 2017). In addition, our efficiency assessment does
454 not rely on a real loss of energy production as such information is rarely available from wind
455 energy developers. [However, as blade speed distributions do not differ between lost blade
456 rotations of both curtailment methods, the relative comparison of lost blade rotations between
457 curtailment methods as a proxy of energy production losses is not biased.](#) Bat activity around
458 nacelles is a good proxy for fatality risk (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2013; Peterson et al., 2021),
459 but we encourage further research on the relationship between activity and mortality to refine
460 algorithms, by giving more weight to conditions in which activity is most strongly correlated
461 with mortality.

462 The strategy of algorithm-based curtailment should be conceived on a large scale to save a
463 global percentage of the bat population from fatality risk, although on some sites the method
464 may currently be less effective. This will require integrated and adaptive management
465 approaches to base curtailment algorithms on a large-scale dataset, while continuing post-
466 construction monitoring to locally refine algorithms when needed. Since temperate
467 insectivorous bat species respond to a documented set of landscape characteristics, weather
468 conditions and seasonality, we expect the development of such curtailment algorithms to be
469 efficient and of great relevance in most temperate ecosystems.

470 Finally, ~~in contrast to the current situation—where in France and many other countries not all
471 wind turbines are subject to curtailment (Roemer et al. 2022)—~~ our study calls for a
472 ~~generalization of wind turbine curtailments as their effect on bat mortality seems to be
473 systematic (Adams et al., 2021; Whitby et al., 2021).~~ We also urge for the use of multicriteria

474 curtailment algorithms instead of basic conventional curtailments as power production is clearly
475 predicted to be higher and the benefit for bats high in most situations (Behr et al., 2017).

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486

487 **Author's contribution**

488 K.B. with the support of C.K. conceived the ideas, designed the methodology, collected and
489 processed the data, and analysed the data; K.B. led writing of the manuscript with the support
490 of all authors. JSPF computed landscape variables. All authors critically contributed to the
491 drafts and gave their final approval for publication.

492

493 **Data accessibility**

494 Data used for analyses will be available on a dedicated platform.

495

496 **Conflict of Interest**

497 France Energie Eolienne (FEE) is an association of more than 300 members, professionals of
498 the wind energy sector in France, who have built more than 90% of the turbines installed on the
499 French territory and operate more than 85% of them. The scientific question was defined with
500 FEE whose members provided the data, FEE had no role in data preparation and analysis,

501 interpretation and discussion of the results, and decision to publish. The Office Français de la
502 Biodiversité (OFB) is a public institution dedicated to the protection and restoration of
503 biodiversity in metropolitan and overseas France, under the authority of the French Ministry of
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505 the manuscript and this proofreading did not influence the interpretations, discussions and
506 conclusions of the study. Corrections made to the first draft following these proofreading can
507 be found at XXXX. Authors take complete responsibility for the accuracy of their analysis and
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511

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714 Figure 1. Location of monitoring sites in France according to bat recorder types.

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716 Figure 2. Percentage of bat activity and occurrence variance explained by each variable (i.e.
 717 pseudo- R^2) related to acoustic method, landscape, weather and time, and wind turbine features
 718 from generalized linear mixed models based on data from all recorder types ([i.e. 59 sites, 14,937](#)
 719 [nights and 98,627 bat passes](#)).

(A) Method for assessing the effectiveness of curtailment methods

(B) Effectiveness of curtailment methods

720

721 Figure 3. Panel A depicts the method to compare wind speed-based (black) and algorithm-
 722 based (blue) curtailment methods effectiveness to limit bat fatality risk, based on 100 iterations
 723 of training generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) on a random selection of 50% of the
 724 [Batmode dataset](#) and predicting bat activity (for LRE and MRE guilds) and occurrence (for
 725 SRE guild) as well as computing recorded bat activity at risk and lost blade rotation on the
 726 remaining 50% (see section 2.4). The method first links the percentage of recorded bat activity
 727 at risk and the percentage of lost blade rotations, respectively, to the wind speed threshold below
 728 which the turbine is stopped (wind speed curtailment) and the predicted bat activity above
 729 which the turbine is stopped (curtailment algorithm). Then the method links the percentage of

730 recorded bat activity at risk and the percentage of lost blade rotations for both curtailment
731 methods to compare their effectiveness presented for the three guilds in the panel B.

733 Figure 4. Predicted number of bat passes or probability of presence from generalized linear
734 mixed models and 95% confidence intervals as a function of significant variables related to
735 landscape (green), wind turbine (grey), and weather and date (blue). [based on the Batmode](#)
736 [dataset](#).

737 Table 1. Estimates, standard errors and p-values from full models testing the effect of landscape,
738 wind turbine and weather/time variables on LRE and MRE activity and SRE occurrence.
739 Missing values indicate that landscape variable was not selected in full models (only the three
740 best explaining ones per guild were included, see Statistical analysis section for more details)
741 or the no need for quadratic or cubic effects on weather/date variables. Significant effects
742 ($P < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Variable	LRE		MRE		SRE	
	Estimate±SE	P	Estimate±SE	P	Estimate±SE	P
Intercept	-0.091±0.237	0.702	-0.492±0.122	<0.001	-6.408±0.373	<0.001
<i>Landscape variables</i>						
Edge density (m/ha, 10,000 m)	-	-	-	-	1.893±0.304	<0.001
Patch richness density (Number per 100 ha, 1,000 m)	-	-	0.608±0.175	0.001	-	-
Arable land proportion (10,000 m)	-	-	-	-	0.623±0.379	0.100
Shannon diversity index (10,000 m)	0.886±0.284	0.002	-	-	-	-
Distance to impervious (m)	-0.168±0.417	0.687	-0.194 ±0.204	0.342	-	-
Impervious proportion (100 m)	-	-	-	-	0.370±0.128	0.004
Distance to forest (m)	-0.181±0.313	0.562	-	-	-	-
Forest proportion (10,000 m)	-	-	0.313±0.119	0.008	-	-
<i>Wind turbine variables</i>						
Rotor diameter (m)	0.033±0.269	0.903	0.037±0.151	0.805	0.694±0.316	0.028
Nacelle height (m)	0.236±0.271	0.383	0.192±0.145	0.185	-0.164±0.320	0.607
Average blade speed (km/h)	0.176±0.129	0.171	-0.751±0.221	0.001	-1.144±0.506	0.024
Average blade speed ²	-0.811±0.156	<0.001	0.402±0.259	0.120	1.744±0.509	0.001
<i>Weather/date variables</i>						
Julian day	0.347±0.033	<0.001	-1.516±0.364	<0.001	0.102±0.130	0.429
Julian day ²	-0.072±0.050	0.150	1.736±0.365	<0.001	-	-
Julian day ³	-0.349±0.033	<0.001	-	-	-	-
Average temperature (°C)	-0.487±0.134	<0.001	2.030±0.222	<0.001	0.239±0.139	0.085
Average temperature ²	1.033±0.127	<0.001	-1.055±0.201	<0.001	-	-
Average wind speed (m/s)	-1.933±0.160	<0.001	-3.272±0.269	<0.001	-1.852±0.582	0.001
Average wind speed ²	1.928±0.156	<0.001	2.751±0.272	<0.001	1.630±0.437	<0.001
Cumulated rain (mm)	-0.176±0.032	<0.001	-0.330±0.052	<0.001	-0.398±0.180	0.027

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